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Ann G. Wellens

Catya A. Zúñiga Alcaraz

DESIGN OF A TOOL TO ALERT MOTORISTS ABOUT THE CONDITIONS OF FLOODED ROADS

Armando Moises Pérez Silva^(a), Verónica Olvera Rodríguez^(b), Idalia Flores de la Mota^(c),
Francisca Soler Anguiano^(d)

^(a) ^(b) ^(c) ^(d) Facultad de Ingeniería, UNAM-MÉXICO

^(a) moy132.perez@gmail.com, ^(b) olvera_veronica@outlook.com, ^(c) idalia@unam.mx,
^(d) fisau34@hotmail.com

ABSTRACT

This article describes the design of an automatic Internet of Things (IoT) alert and real-time measurement of the level of water accumulated by floods. A flood can obstruct major roads; as is the case in Mexico City, where every year during the rainy season floods cause road chaos, paralyze public and private transport and damage material resources. The proposed sensor system is complemented by an application for mobile devices, through which users can be notified about the water levels on the roads, to avoid traveling through risk areas. The application will create a synergy between the different users, by notifying the types of vehicles (cars, vans or buses) that, depending on their height, are able to pass through the flooded area, preventing said vehicles from suffering mechanical damage, being partially immersed or dragged by the current. On the other hand, users may decide to use their vehicle to travel or choose another transport system to reach their destination. These measures will help to reduce the saturation of roads and allow emergency vehicles such as ambulances to reach their destination faster.

Keywords: IoT technology, flood contingency plan, optimization, smart cities.

1. INTRODUCTION

Flooding in cities is one of the most frequent natural hazards and one of the most disruptive in terms of mobility and logistics, which means that hundreds or thousands of people and products cannot reach their destinations and remain stranded for hours.

In Mexico City, because of climate change, atmospheric phenomena have increased their intensity, frequency and duration. Because of this situation, in 2011 a decree was passed enacting the law on mitigation and adaptation to climate change and sustainable development (Asamblea Legislativa del Distrito Federal, 2011). It has been empirically estimated that Mexico City's deep drains cannot drain off at a rate higher than 40 mm/h and any higher rate may cause flooding (Landa, 2008), so contingency plans for rain and floods must be dynamic and adaptable to the circumstances presented by this phenomenon. This paper proposes a real-time monitoring system that includes users and enables them to anticipate

the threats caused by road flooding and keep abreast of changes in water levels on the roads.

1.1. Background

Mexico City, like other countries in Latin America and the Caribbean, is affected by extreme weather events. In the Dominican Republic, Ecuador and Bolivia there have been increased floods. These countries have implemented an Early Warning System (SAT) consisting of four elements: 1) knowledge of the risks they face, 2) systematic observation, 3) communication and alert, dissemination of warnings to people at risk; and 4) preparedness and response measures to generate public awareness and readiness to act. In these countries, the existence of a planning and response mechanism to deal with floods has been evident, to move from a disaster approach to a comprehensive risk perspective. However, there is still a gap between technical forecasting / monitoring and community communication / response (Del Granado, 2016).

In Barranquilla, there is a high risk of death and material losses associated with flash floods in the city streets (Cama-Pinto, 2016). So a wireless sensor network was designed to monitor flash floods, through the wireless architecture or sensor network WSN (Wireless Sensor network) to monitor real-time atmospheric parameters that influence the water levels, detecting the danger of flash floods caused by sudden and heavy rainfall in a short period of time.

The flash flood early warning (FFEW) has drawn worldwide attention for its outstanding practicality and economic efficiency. Developing countries have built several operational FFEW systems adapted to certain regions with specific input data. FFEW systems involve long-term and real-time flash flood warnings. Long-term warnings predict the risk of flash flood disasters on a long timescale. Real-time warnings forecast the probability of flash flooding over a short timescale, such as a day or a few hours, and are commonly used in emergency situations (Li, 2018).

In China, research into real-time flash flood warnings on the FFEW system uses computational methods for real-time warning indicators, improving the data sources used for warnings and the automation of real-time warning systems.

1.2. Early flood detection in Mexico City

The Mexico City government currently has two tools for warning and informing the population during the rainy season about how to avoid flooding and to protect their families. These tools are:

- Early meteorological warning, a tool developed by Civil Defense (Protección Civil, 2017). The alert helps citizens to have at least 15 minutes of advantage warning to take preventive actions for the greater safety to their family and property.
- Rainstorm warning signals, this tool can be found on the website of the Mexico City Water System (Sacmex) shows a list of the 16 municipalities indicating the intensity of the rainfall (Atlas de riesgo, 2019).

1.3. Internet of Things (IoT)

The Internet of Things (IoT) refers to those objects, animals, plants, humans and, in general, "things" that have an internet connection anytime and anywhere. Technically, it consists of the integration and interconnection of a set of sensors and microcontrollers with objects over a wireless network. Because of the increasing availability of Internet access and connection, the adoption of IoT is also increasingly feasible. Moreover, the low costs allow an easy integration of sensors in various environments, which implies that every object can be a source of data and information.

The IoT phenomenon has opened up around us, giving life to everyday objects that are interconnected thanks to the Network and that constitute inexhaustible sources of information. For this, it has been necessary to combine three phenomena that enable users to the use IoT. First of all, the growing miniaturization of computer components, making it easy to connect virtually anything, from anywhere, at any time.

Secondly, overcoming the limitation of mobile telephony infrastructure and lastly, the proliferation of applications and services that put the large amount of information created from the IoT into use.

With the IoT, small sensors are integrated into real-world objects and provide information on virtually everything that can be measured. In this way, we are increasingly interconnected, and people and objects can interact completely differently. Today there are one billion Internet users, 4,000 million people with mobile phones and an endless list of objects (cars, appliances, cameras, etc.) connected to the Internet in one way or another. "Intelligent" environments are built around this and are capable of analyzing, diagnosing and executing functions, eliminating possible human errors (FIB, 2011).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The research focuses on two technological aspects: the implementation of IoT and the use of a specific application for the identification and early notification of flooding on certain roads. For the use of IoT, authors like González (2017) explain how so-called Smart Cities are a field where there is extensive use of IoT through devices that collect the greatest amount of data to

facilitate the life of the inhabitants. There is also Smart Traffic, which consists of giving real-time information about the traffic and proposing alternative routes.

Nowadays there are some flood detectors, mainly for domestic use, on the market (retrieved from Tunstall, 2019), (retrieved from Fibaro, 2019), but there are some others with wider uses, as (retrieved from LoRa and LoRaWA, 2019). There is also a site (FLOOD NETWORK, Building the UK's biggest network of flood sensors, 2019) where they explain what they offer: "Our low-cost wireless sensors harness the power of the Internet of Things to give you updates about waterways, culverts, rivers, ditches and even groundwater. They're battery powered and connect wirelessly to a gateway which sends the data back to our system using the Internet. A web map visualises your waterways and their levels at <https://map.flood.network>".

It is important to mention that all these devices use IoT. So, based on this information, what this paper proposes is an ultrasonic device that detects the level of water, whose operation consists of emitting an ultrasonic sound through one of its transducers, and waiting for the sound to bounce of any object that is present with a second transducer picking up the echo. The sensor can detect objects, distance or level at a minimum range of 2 cm to a maximum of 400 cm. It can be used, for example, for different types of projects such as proximity alarms, measuring water levels of a water tank or any other object that stores some kind of liquid. This sensor, created by the authors, is currently in the experimental phase.

3. METHODOLOGY

The methodology used for this research is as follows:

3.1 Information gathering

According to UNAM researcher, Ramón Domínguez (2000), in his study whose title translates as "Floods in Mexico City. Problem and Solution Alternatives", the problem of flooding occurs mainly on roads that are below the Western Intercept Drain, where the collectors have lost gradient; this is from the Periférico to Avenida de los Insurgentes. This study analyzes the problem of flooding in the Valley of Mexico, based on a historical perspective that, in essence, shows that the problem has been recurring since the time of the Aztecs, for which a solution has always been sought that does not involve stopping the growth of urbanization in the valley. But it is also true that the "solutions" have never been preventive, but have been developed following catastrophic floods. On the other hand, the Mexico City Water System (Sacmex, 2017) together with the authorities of Mexico City have identified 48 neighborhoods and 136 points of high risk of flooding when there are heavy rains that exceed the capacity of the sewer system. These points are mainly concentrated in the Iztapalapa and Gustavo A. Madero municipalities, where the 18 high-risk flood neighborhoods are concentrated. But there are also critical points in Miguel Hidalgo, Álvaro Obregón, Azcapotzalco, Magdalena Contreras and Benito Juárez.

For his part, Omar Diaz (2019), in his interview with Bernardo Carmona, general director of the Mexico City

Water System, highlights the areas where there is a high probability of flooding in the different municipalities of Mexico City, namely: Iztapalapa 640, Gustavo A. Madero 402, Cuauhtémoc 298, Venustiano Carranza 290, Iztacalco 218, Coyoacán 198, Azcapotzalco 168 and Tláhuac 15. These numbers represent areas per municipality.

3.2 The identification of the problem

The problem was identified through the analysis of the information collected, considering the following:

- There are areas that have recurring problems irrespective of how much rain falls. This is because of the unevenness of the area and / or the concentration of large quantities of garbage that prevent rainwater from flowing freely through the drainage.
- Affected roads: this occurs when there is flooding that, depending on the area, ranges from moderate to intense.
- Material damage such as: lifting of the asphalt pavement, potholes, partial or total damage to cars, among other things.
- Total or partial blockage of roads derived from: broken-down cars and high water levels during flooding.
- Emergency vehicles being blocked as the result of road paralysis.

3.3 Proposed solution

While analyzing the problems caused by floods and waterlogging in various roads in Mexico City, an alternative solution emerged. This solution consists of the integration of IoT technologies to monitor in real time the level of water on some of the roads on a route and determining whether or not the cars, depending on their size, will be able to pass through it without the risk of being stranded in the attempt. This solution is complemented by an application for mobile devices that allows the user to know the status of monitored roads by indicating the level of water so that vehicles can circulate, in addition to having a signal that shows water levels. Currently the Mexico City Water System (SACMEX) has implemented an intensity signal for each city municipality (Figure 1) that warns the population about the general situation of the different districts, however, it does not indicate the level of flooding on the affected roads and, above all, does not issue recommendations on the type of vehicles that can circulate along the road, as with the current proposal. These types of recommendations are very important as they will enable users to decide in advance on the route that they should choose to arrive safely at their destination; not block the roads where only taller vehicles, such as buses, cargo transport or emergency vehicles, such as ambulances, are allowed; and, when necessary, to choose an alternative means of transport (bus, Metro or Metrobús) to avoid the unnecessary congestion of roads.

3.4 Simulation

The proposed solution is supported by simulation in SIMIO software, where values are assigned to the

different variables, such as: type of vehicle (car, van and bus) in relation to its height, original road, alternative road available, fault in the system (flooding of the road) and probability of a successful crossing for each type of vehicle (Figure. 2).

Figure 1. Rainfall warning signal. Source: SACMEX, (2019).

Figure 2. Simulation of road flooding. Source: the authors.

Figure 3 shows the flow of vehicles on the roads without the presence of any fault in the system (floods).

Figure 3. Vehicle flow without flooding. Source: the authors.

The simulation also finds the saturation of the roads when there is a fault in the system (floods). Figure 3 shows how, by having an alternative road (maintained in good

conditions), the vehicle flow increases but does not stagnate as on the flooded roads. This is because the various vehicles choose the alternate route in advance in order to avoid being stranded in traffic caused by floods. From the results obtained from the simulation, we conclude that real-time monitoring of the level of flood water and giving timely information to motorists makes it possible to reduce the number of vehicles left stranded and obstructing the affected roads.

4. DESIGN OF THE DEVICE

The proposed monitoring system consists of a set of devices connected through a Wi-Fi network with a database, where each device sends the corresponding information about the monitored variable (water level in this case, as shown in figure 4).

Figure 4. Wi-Fi network devices. Source: the authors.

The system receives the data, verifies the value of the variable and associates it with a high, medium or low water level. This system is based on an ESP chip that enables connection to existing WiFi networks and is easy to program on the Arduino platform, free software that facilitates the creation of electronic prototypes. Development cards based on the Arduino programming platform can support many elements, such as different types of sensors, thanks to their ports composed of pins that can be programmatically configured as inputs or outputs, making it possible to capture information about the environment through different types of sensors.

The proposed monitoring system works as follows:

1. The ESP chip connects to a Wi-Fi network.
2. Through serial communication, the ESP chip collects the information about the variable coming from an ultrasonic sensor (as illustrated in the figure 5).
3. The information collected is verified in the chip through specific structures that ensure the accuracy of the data. If the measured values do not match the expected data, a new sampling is performed to avoid errors.
4. The data collected through the sensors are sent and stored in a database on the "cloud" (external database servers) as shown in figure 6. This data is updated in real time throughout the event, this way it is possible to know if water levels are rising or falling.

Figure 5. Ultrasonic sensor data acquisition. Source: the authors

Figure 6. Database with stored data. Source: the authors.

The application for mobile devices accesses the information stored in the database, interprets it and displays a value corresponding to the probability of a vehicle being able to cross a flooded street or avenue, as shown in figure 7.

Figure 7. Probability, interpreted by WebApp, of a vehicle being able to cross a flooded street. Source: the authors

The proposed system is conceptualized, in its simplest form, as a set of sensors that collect data and communicate it to a microcontroller that processes the

data and sends it to a database via Wi-Fi, then to be retrieved and interpreted by an application for mobile devices for the users to use, as shown in figure 8.

Figure 8. Proposed system in its simplest form. Source: the authors.

5. RAIN MONITOR

Rain Monitor is an app developed by students from the systems engineering postgraduate unit, aimed at contributing to the mitigation of the effects and consequences caused by flooding on the different roads of Mexico City.

The proposed device collects information on the level of water accumulated in the streets, this water level is acquired through an ultrasonic sensor which transduces the energy received by means of ultrasonic waves and transmits them to the microcontroller in the form of digital pulses. For its part, the microcontroller receives the signal, processes it and emits the results to the ESP microcontroller via serial communication. Then, the ESP microcontroller sends the data via internet to a database hosted on the “cloud” (databases hosted on external data servers).

The rain monitor is a WebApp responsible for recovering the data stored in the cloud database and presenting them in numerical (probability) and graphic form. This WebApp makes it possible to know the flood levels on the different routes so users can select the route with the optimal water levels for their type of vehicle.

5.1. App features

The main feature of this application is that it is not designed as a native application, that is, it is not developed for a particular operating system, instead, the application is based on a WebApp where a web page is basically adapted so “Responsive”, that means attached to any type of screen of the different mobile devices.

The different advantages of that WebApp include:

- Display on any operating system: it has no problem adapting to iOS, Android, among others.
- It does not need to be installed from App stores, such as Google Play Store or Apple App Store. That means a saving, as the direct link through a Web Approximately is free.
- Development time is also shorter.

Figure 9 and figure 10 show the WebApp developed for mobile device screens and PC desktop screens respectively. The graphs shown indicate the probability of success for a vehicle crossing a street or avenue with a level of flooding.

Figure 9. View of mobile device screen. Source: the authors.

Figure 10. PC desktop view. Source: the authors.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The design and application of tools that permit the real-time monitoring of areas affected by floods is important for determining the scope of the emergency, reducing material losses and adjusting an action plan to take another route or means of transport.

The increasing use of technology based on the internet of things or "IoT" allows us to interconnect many elements. This interconnection seeks to create the connection between the real world and the virtual world, whose purpose is to integrate the parts of a system. In the case of cities, these technologies can improve the quality of life of its inhabitants through an efficient and responsible management of their resources, enabling them to face future challenges. In this paper, the design and implementation of applications based on IoT tools that allow the real-time monitoring of flood-affected areas are important for determining the scale of the emergency, reducing material losses and adjusting an action plan for taking another route or means of transport.

In the future work we plan to make an analysis of networks that let users know the routes that are not saturated for reaching their destination. On the other hand, it is advisable to perform a risk analysis to determine the hazards as well as the present and emerging risks that can be subsequently evaluated, quantified and even modeled, to finally conclude with the implementation of control and mitigation plans aimed at safeguarding the well-being of the population.

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